

The Influence of Social Media on Students' Academic Performance in Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi

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Abstract:- The research examined the influence of social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, 2go, Pinterest, LinkedIn, TikTok and others) on academic performance of students of Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. Three research questions and three research objectives guided the study. To achieve this, a descriptive survey research design was carried out amongst students of the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, which has a population of 20, 000 full students at the time of the study. A simple random sampling using the Creative Research System Software (CRSS) at a confidence level of 95% was used to select the sample of 100 students. Survey questionnaires were administered to collect data from students. The descriptive statistics of frequency was used to analyse the demographic data. The research findings revealed that a large percentage of students rely on social media for information that aid their studies. However, students also spend significant time on social media networking other than academic purposes. Thus, the impact of social networking is both positive and negative. Therefore, it is recommended that managements of higher institutions device measures to encourage students on how best to utilise social media to maximum academic performance.

Keywords:- Social Media, Networking, Influence, Performance, Academic.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of social media has altered patterns of lives of human beings and connected the world in terms of access to information more than ever. Imene (2017) defines social media as the collective of online communications channels dedicated to community-based input, interaction, content-sharing and collaboration. There are many social media and social networking platforms nowadays such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitters, YouTube, Instagram, Tik Tok, LinkedIn which enable people access information and ideas. In 2023, an estimated 4.9 million people world-wide use social media, with China having the most social media users of 1.02 billion (Ruby, 2023).

According to the World Bank (2023), Nigeria has an estimated population of 213 million people. The number of internet users in the country increased from 19 million between 2020 and 2021. There were 33 million social media users in Nigeria in January 2021 (Kepios, 2021). The number of social media users in country is currently 38.47

(Ruby, 2023). A significant portion of social media users are students of higher institutions. Findings indicate that student's attitude towards social media has a corresponding impact on performance (Ahmad, 2019; Owusu-Acheaw, 2004; Osharive, 2015).

Social media users use mobile phones or laptop computers to access the internet. The student has an array of networks on social media to access through numerous platforms such as, Facebook, 2go, Twitter, Google, WhatsApp, TikTok, LinkedIn. The culture of social networking presents new ways of doing things especially among young persons with tremendous consequences. Ahmad & Murad (2020) found that social media was key in spreading fear and panic related to COVID-19 outbreak, with negative influence on people's mental health. Wise & Shorter (2014) maintained that social media can be used for both good and bad purposes. Rouse (2012) argues that social media has become an integral part of human interaction as engagement with websites, search engines, and applications to gain knowledge on virtually all subjects increases. Thus, the influence of social media on the academic performance becomes an issue of interest to sociologists because undergraduate and postgraduate students frequently engage with media platforms that offer a wide range of options from entertainment to intellectual engagement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There is no commonly accepted definition of social media, functionally and theoretically speaking because most scholars assume an inherent understanding of social media based on extant technology (Carr and Hayes, 2015). This lack of understanding often leads to limited understanding of the uses and effects of social media. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) describe social media as a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundation of Web 2.0 that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated contents. According to Encyclopedia Britannica (2023), social media are communications on the Internet (such as on websites for social networking and microblogging) through which users share information, ideas, personal messages, and other content. Kim, Sohn & Choi (2010) have found out that the ways people use social media and their reasons for doing so may differ based on their culture and values. Their findings suggest that the major motives for using social network sites – seeking friends, social support, entertainment, information, and

convenience – are similar between two countries, but the weights placed on these motives are different. Aksoy (2018) found that one reason for addiction to social media was the need to socialize, while male participants were more interested in acquiring new friends, female participants were more interested in communicating with their real life friends.

A study by Knight-McCord et al. (2016) showed that College students rely on the Internet generally and social media sites specifically to connect with others through platforms such as Instagram, Snapchat, Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok. Their findings revealed that students spend 76 percent of their time on social networking sites 1-10 hours each day and a slightly larger proportion 80 percent indicated they use the sites more on the weekend. Students are most likely to use social networking sites that enable them to post pictures and videos. Nanin et al (2023) in their study of undergraduates warn that lack of regulatory policies controlling the use of social media/networks in Nigerian universities can lead to abuse and misuse of social media by students.

Studies on the impact of social media on academic performance of students in Nigeria have been well-documented (Asharive, 2015; Ebere & Oghenetega, 2014; Ahmad, 2019). There appears to be a general consensus among scholars that although social media can enhance the academic performance of students if engaged appropriately. However, the lack of regulation of social media can produce opposite results. This is because social media has both positive and negative effects on academic grades.

Almogren (2023) suggests that since social engagement and interaction have always been significantly impacted by collaborative learning and social media use, authorities of higher institutions of learning may decide whether or not to implement an actual usage of social media for academic purposes in educational institutions.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

Since the emergence of social media in the 1990s, the number of social media users in Nigeria has risen from roughly 28 million in 2020 (Statistica.com, 2021) to 38.47 (Ruby, 2023) in 2023. According to studies (Bukhari et al, 2019; Osharive (2015) students spend time on social media covering significant percentage of their daily activities and in turn provides positive significant impact toward their performance. It is not an understatement to argue that a great number of students are addicted to social media. It is on this background that the study was carried out to examine the influence of social media on academic performance of students of Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

- To investigate the reasons for using social media by students.
- To examine the influence of social media on students' performance.
- To identify how social media can improve students' performance.

➤ *Research Questions*

- This study addressed the following research questions.
- What are the reasons students use social media?
 - What are the effects of social media on academic performance of students?
 - How can social media improve students' performance?

➤ *Importance of the Study*

The findings of the study will hopefully add to existing body of knowledge and serve as reference material for other researchers who engage in related studies. The study findings can set the agenda for further inquiries into the influence of social media on students' grade. The research may also offer suitable path on how to address the problem identified.

➤ *Scope of the Study*

The study was restricted to the investigation of the influence of social media on academic performance of students of the Federal Polytechnic Bauchi. The study is concern about the impact of social media on the performance of students. The study was limited to the institution due to time and financial constraints.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The focus of the study was to ascertain the influence of social media on academic performance of students. To accomplish this purpose, the study adopted a cross sectional survey research design among students of Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. This type of research method gives room for a wide range of methods to recruit participants, collect data, and utilise various methods of instrumentation (Ponto, 2015). The study took a descriptive form that simply describes behaviour or attitudes of students towards social media. The Academic Records Office of the Polytechnic disclosed that Polytechnic had a total population of 20,000 students at the time the study was carried out in 2013.

➤ *Sample Size/Sampling Technique*

A sample size was determined using the Creative Research System Software (CRSS) at a confidence level of 95%. Survey questionnaires were administered to 100 students selected across the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. The sample for the study used the cluster \ sampling technique. Cluster sampling technique is preferred because participants that represent the population are identified and included in the sample (Jackson, 2011). The Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, comprised of several faculties and departments. However, for the study, students were purposively selected from the Faculties of Agriculture, Arts, Science, and Management & Social Science. Respondents were subsequently drawn from departments namely Agriculture Extension, Biology, Biochemistry, Mass Communication, Computer Science, Public Administration, Accounting, Business Administration. For the sample size, a total of 100 questionnaires were administered to participants. Cluster sample was employed at the faculty to group the population of study. Students from each department was selected using random sampling. This was achieved through cluster sampling. The students were all in

various levels, ages, gender and used different devices such as laptops and mobile phones to engage with social network services.

Winner and Dominick (2000) defined sample as a representative group from the population to serve as a respondent. Therefore, in the conduct of the study, samples of five students were randomly selected from different levels and departments in the Federal Polytechnic Bauchi. The random sampling allowed each and every respondents of the population to be represented in the study. The sample comprised male and female students randomly picked from the selected departments. That means participants were be drawn from ND to HND levels such that all levels were represented in the study.

➤ *Instrument of Data Collection/ Questionnaire Format*

The main instrument for the data collection for this study was structured questionnaire, comprised of 10 items and two sections. Section (A) contains Bio data of the respondents while section (B) contains the three research questions.

The questionnaire format was designed to find out the influence of social media on the performance of students. The first section contains personal data of the respondents. To establish feeling of confidentiality, names and other necessary information about the respondents were avoided. The second part of the questionnaire contains closed ended question on the influence of social media on academic performance of the students.

The researcher administered 100 copies of the structured questionnaire randomly by selecting respondents from different departments and levels. The researcher explained the purpose for the study and directly answered the questions that might be raised by the respondents as regards the questionnaire.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Data collected from the study was grouped in accordance with answers given by the participants. The result was expected to answer the research questions. The study applied descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage in computing the results. The data presentation was drawn from the completed structure questionnaire. For this study a total of 100 questionnaires were distributed to students in National Diploma (ND) and High National Diploma (HND) of the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi for the 2012/2013 academic session. A total of 13 questionnaires were returned invalid because they were not properly filled, therefore the data analysis for this research was based on the 87 copies that were properly filled and returned. The responses were tallied and built into simple frequency (F) and percentage (%). The participants selected for the study were of various age range. However, age (21-25) years were 37, which represented 34% and made up the majority of the participants. The respondents undergoing Higher National Diploma (HND) selected for the study were 47 or 54 % while 40 participants representing 46% were undergoing National Diploma (ND) programme. While 46 participants

representing 53 % were male, the female participants were 41 which constitutes 47% of the respondents. On awareness of social media, 95% of participants were aware of and use social media, while only 4 participants or 5 % said they were not aware of social media or any social network platform. This means social media is popular among students of the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi because 95% engage with social networks on daily basis while only 5% do not use or browse any social media network. It can be deduced from responses of the respondents that Facebook was most popular among students out of the social network services. From their responses, 60 participants, representing 69% said they preferred Facebook among all the social networks; while 14 use twitter, 7% engage with YouTube, and only 10% prefer 2go.

Based on responses, the majority of the respondents' said they accessed social media to get information that can boost their academic performance. From their responses, 41 respondents or 47 % admitted that they used social media to get information for studies, while 5% said they used it to make friends, and 7 % said the purpose of using it was for entertainment.

The responses of participants indicated that the frequency of engagement with social media by students of Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, was high. This is because 43% of the respondents admitted that they browsed the internet three times or more daily while 32% engaged with their favorite social network service at least twice every day, only 25% said they use social media once in a day. While 18 respondents said they used their mobile phone to access social media, 12 used the laptop while It is evident from their responses that the majority of respondents used their mobile phones for social media. This is because 49 of participants which constitute 56 said so, while 14% of them use their laptops, and 28% utilizes all devices, only 2% uses computer in the café.

Table 1: Influence of Social Media on academic performance.

Category	Respondent	F	%
A	Yes	76	87
B	No	11	13
	Total	87	100

Field study Federal Polytechnic Bauchi 2014

As Table 1 shows,76 participants which constitute 87% replied the question in the affirmative, while 11 participants or 13% believed the social media has little or no influence in the academic performance. Therefore, responses show clearly that social media influences students' academic performance.

Table 2. Negative/Positive Influence of Social Media

Category	Respondent	F	%
A	Positively	70	80
B	Negatively	17	20
	Total	87	100

Source: Field Study Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, 2014

Results of responses from Table 2 on the negative/positive influence of social media, out of 87 participants, 70 participants or 80% believed that social has positive influence on the academic performance while 17 respondents representing 20% said they were skeptical of social media because it has negative impact on their academia performance.

Table 3: Positive Influence of Social Media

Category	Respondent	F	%
A	It helps me to get academic material	37	43
B	It impacts knowledge and ideas	25	29
C	It allows me to interact with friends	25	29
	Total	87	100

Source: Field Study Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, 2014

From results of Table 3 above, the majority of respondents (37) or 43 percent explained that social media assisted them to access academic materials, 29% disclosed that social media helped them in terms of acquiring more knowledge and ideas, while another 25 respondents or 29% said social media allowed them to interact with friends.

Table 4: Negatively Influence of Social Media

Category	Respondent	F	%
A	It distract me from academic activities	22	25
B	It consume my time	17	20
C	It infringes on my privacy	4	5
D	It corrupt morality	11	13
	Total	87	100

Source: Field Study Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, 2014

Table 4 shows that 22 respondents (25%) confirmed negative impact on social media on their academic performance. This is because they admitted social media distracted them in their academic pursuit. The 17 respondents (20%) in this category said that social media consumed their time while 4 respondents (5%) said social media infringed on their privacy. However, 11 respondents who constitute 13% said social media caused immoral behaviour in students.

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section takes a close look at the three research questions raised with a view to linking them with the findings of the study. On the reasons or purpose for use of social media by students, question 4 of the questionnaire answered that question. From the responses elicited by the question, the majority of students used social media for academic information. This is because 41% of respondents said they engaged with to social networks to get information, 5% said they browsed through social media to make friends, 7% said use social media for entertainment while 34% disclosed that they used social networks for all of the above reasons. The 2nd research question sought to know the extent of the usage of social media, amongst students. The aim was to find out the time students spend

daily on social media. Question 5 in the structured questionnaire had been able to answer the research question. This is seen where 43% of the respondents which constitute the majority disclosed that they browsed their favorite social networks three times or more every day, while 32% logged on to social media twice daily, only 25% browsed once in a day. Research Question 3 intended to uncover how social media influences students' academic performance The aim was to ascertain the impact of social media on academic performance of student either positively or negatively. Thus questions 7, 8, 9 and 10 in the administered questionnaires were able to answer this question. 80% of the student replied that social media had impacted on their academic performance. 20% of the respondents said they were affected negatively by the use of social media. Those who said social media affected their studies positively, represented 80% who revealed that, social media impacted knowledge and ideas on them. Those who were affected negatively constituting 20% confessed that social media consumed their useful time. It could therefore be concluded, based on the responses, that social media have in negative impact on them 25% of the respondent admitting social media was a distraction in academic activities.

VI. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research was intended to study the influence of social media) on the academic performance of students of the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. The study, which was carried out in 2013, discovered that social media use influences the academic performance of the students of the Polytechnic in more positive than negative ways. Though participants who responded to the administered questionnaires were divided in opinions, the majority of the participants, the study found out, were affected positively by social media.

The methodology the research employed was the survey design method where the research population was identified, and the sampling techniques as well as the research instrument used in acquiring the data were all explained. The data was gathered, analyzed and interpreted and the findings of the research related with the research questions to ensure they had really answered the research questions which they actually did.

The analysis of data gathered has clearly revealed that social media has impact on the academic performance of the students of the Federal Polytechnic Bauchi (FPTB). Almost all the participants knew and engaged social media network services daily except a marginal few who do not use social media. The majority of the respondents admitted that social media had positive impact on their academic performance because it helped them to get materials for academic purposes. Some respondents believed that social media distracted them from their academic activities. Thus the use of social media by the students of tertiary institutions should not be totally discouraged because it serves as major source of academic information and resource materials for academic purposes including but not limited to assignments, paper presentations, seminars, class tests, projects among

others. It is obvious that students benefit tremendously from social media because besides aiding their academics, social media give them platform to interact, make new friends, stay connected with old friends and build social relationships. It is however important to stress that social media if not well regulated can be abused and detrimental to students. Social media can lead to loss of concentration to the extent that it can negatively temper with their overall performance of students.

➤ Summary

This study intended to establish the influence of social media on the academic performance of students of the Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. It was discovered that social media affects the academic performance of the students in more positive than negative ways. The methodology the research employed was the survey design method where the research population was identified, and a sampling technique as well as the research instrument used in acquiring the data were all explained. The data was gathered, analyzed and interpreted and the findings of the research related with the research objective to ensure they had really addressed the problem.

➤ Conclusion

The analysis of data gathered clearly revealed that social media has influence both positively and negatively on the academic performance of students. Almost all students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria are aware and conversant with usage of social media except for few. Most A level students believe the social media is useful and has positive impact on their academic performance because it helped them to get materials for academic purposes. They however believed that it can also serve as a veritable source of distraction to students in their academic pursuit. Thus the use of social media by the students should not be discouraged as it can provide sources of materials for their academic activities such as assignments, paper presentations, seminars, tests and projects among others.

Although it is obvious that students benefit tremendously from social media where they not only acquire study resources, it also serves as an avenue for social interactions. It is however important to stress that it can also affect students' concentration to the extent that it tempers with their overall performance. For instance, the majority of the students in the study admitted that they visit the net three time and more every day, a time that could have been spent on studying.

➤ Recommendations

The following recommendations on the social media use by students are hereby suggested. Firstly, students should be taught the technicalities of maximizing the social media for academic exploits by the management of higher institutions. This is mainly to facilitate knowledge through social networks mainly by acquiring relevant information and ideas that will help boost in their academic activities. Secondly, students should be enlightened or softly restrict in the duration they spend daily on social network to enable them get time for studies. Thus, students should be posting important academic information on their various platforms

that will be useful to other members of the group. Students should know the kind of friends they make and the relationship they build on the social media. Thirdly, the Federal Ministry of Information and other relevant government agencies and regulatory bodies should ensure that students are properly educated and enlightened to browse through social media to improve their academic performance. Fourthly, the paper suggests that further research can be carried out on the subject with a view to introducing a new dimension to the topic with a views to addressing issues that arise from misused of social media solutions.

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